

Researchers in the Private Sector in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "Research talent, % in businesses" in the Global Innovation Index represents the percentage of research and development (R&D) talent employed within a country's private sector. This indicator measures a country's ability to attract and retain skilled personnel for research activities in private businesses, reflecting the degree of integration between academia and industry. A high percentage of research talent in businesses is often correlated with an innovation-friendly environment, where companies invest in human capital to develop new products, technologies, and processes. A high value in this variable indicates that a country has a specialized workforce embedded in businesses, capable of responding to the demands of an increasingly competitive global market. Conversely, a low percentage may suggest challenges within the private sector in attracting qualified talent for R&D, possibly due to a lack of investment, infrastructure, or attractive career opportunities. Thus, "Research talent, % in businesses" is a key indicator for understanding a country's innovative capacity and the strategic role of businesses in supporting and promoting applied research, essential for global economic competitiveness. The data refers to the period between 2016 and 2022.

R&D Talent in the Private Sector in the Global Innovation Index 2022. The 2022 Global Innovation Index data on the variable "Research talent, % in businesses" shows how the percentage of research talent employed in private companies varies significantly across countries, reflecting the level of private sector involvement in research and development (R&D) activities. At the top of the rankings is South Korea, with a value of 100%, indicating that all research talent is employed in private companies. This reflects a strong integration between academia and industry and South Korea's capacity to attract researchers into companies to develop advanced technologies and globally competitive products. Close behind are the United Arab Emirates at 95.1%, demonstrating a growing

commitment from the private sector to drive innovation, supported by government policies aimed at diversifying the economy beyond the energy sector. Japan (91.3%), the United States (88.3%), and Sweden (87.8%) also show high values, indicating innovation-driven economies with significant private sector participation in research. Countries like the Netherlands (86.1%), Turkey (79.3%), and Austria (76.8%) solidify their positions as innovation hubs with private R&D investments, showcasing a business culture that promotes research and collaboration with academia. In Europe, countries such as France (76.8%), Germany (73.5%), and Finland (72.1%) maintain high percentages, confirming the private sector's ability to support advanced research activities. China also ranks well at 71.4%, indicating a rapidly transforming economy where private companies play a crucial role in technological development, supported by favorable government policies and growing domestic innovation support. In the mid-range, countries like Italy (59.1%) and Switzerland (58.9%) show moderate percentages of research talent employed in businesses. These countries could benefit from increased private sector participation to accelerate technological progress and strengthen industrial competitiveness. The United Kingdom, at 50.9%, ranks slightly below other advanced economies, suggesting room for improvement in integrating researchers into the private sector and fostering greater collaboration between companies and academic institutions. At the lower end of the rankings are emerging and developing countries like Morocco (8.2%), Egypt (7.4%), and Rwanda (6.5%), which show low percentages of research talent employed in the private sector. These figures suggest that research remains primarily concentrated in public or academic institutions, while private companies, often constrained by financial resources and inadequate structures, struggle to employ researchers for R&D activities. Countries like Colombia (2.8%) and Ethiopia (2.3%) have particularly low values, indicating a lack of infrastructure and incentives to attract qualified talent to the private sector. In conclusion, the data reveals a significant disparity in countries' ability to integrate research talent into private companies. Countries with high percentages of private sector researchers tend to have highly competitive economies, where innovation is supported by strong collaboration between universities and industry. In contrast, countries with low percentages could benefit from targeted incentives and support policies to strengthen the role of private companies in research, thereby enhancing their national innovation potential.

R&D Talent in the Private Sector in the Global Innovation Index from 2016 to 2022. The Global Innovation Index data from 2016 to 2022 for the variable "Research talent, % in businesses" reveals significant changes in the percentage of research talent employed in private companies across various countries, highlighting both marked improvements and declines. Some countries have registered substantial increases, indicating progress in integrating qualified personnel in research and development (R&D) within the private sector, while others have experienced drastic reductions, reflecting potential economic challenges or shifts in private sector priorities. Among the top performers, Ethiopia (+360%) and Colombia (+211%) show the highest increases, rising from very low initial values (0.5 and 0.9) to still limited percentages in 2022 (2.3 and 2.8, respectively). Countries like North Macedonia (+143%) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (+113%) also show notable gains, indicating growing interest in R&D within private companies. Bulgaria (+91.4%) and Cyprus (+78.2%) demonstrate similarly significant advances in the presence of research talent in the private sector, reflecting a strategy aimed at improving innovation capacity through the direct employment of specialized personnel. This increase may be linked to targeted government policies or incentives to stimulate collaboration between academia and industry. Southeast Asian countries, such as Thailand (+72.2%), show encouraging gains, with the private sector playing an increasingly central role in research activities. Likewise, Greece (+69.2%), Croatia (+67%), and Poland (+63.6%) have seen growth in the percentage of research talent employed in businesses, indicating increased competitiveness and value placed on corporate innovation. On the other hand, several countries have shown a marked decline in the percentage of research talent employed in companies. Some, like Indonesia (-79.2%) and Uganda (-92.5%), reveal clear difficulties in retaining and attracting qualified talent in the private sector, possibly due to limited resources or a lack of adequate infrastructure for corporate research. The drastic drop in Indonesia and Uganda, from moderate levels (42.4 and 60.4

in 2016) to very low levels (8.8 and 4.5 in 2022), suggests a significant loss of competitiveness in the private sector. Countries like Ireland (-13%) and Ukraine (-21.4%) also show concerning declines, especially given that they started from higher levels of corporate research percentages. These figures could indicate internal economic difficulties or reduced emphasis on private sector research. Similarly, nations like Qatar (-41.9%) and Montenegro (-40.5%) have faced significant reductions, which may reflect structural changes or a reallocation of national resources toward other priority areas. In summary, the data reveals a sharp contrast: some countries are increasingly investing in the integration of research talent within the private sector, demonstrating a strategic commitment to innovation, while others face challenges that hinder researcher participation in businesses. This gap could have long-term implications for global economic competitiveness and affect countries' ability to lead and adapt to technological changes.

Conclusions. The average percentage of researchers employed in businesses, as indicated in the Global Innovation Index, increased by 6.32%, rising from 42.95% to 45.67%. The top-performing countries are Ethiopia with +360.00%, Colombia with +211.11%, North Macedonia with +143.16%, Bosnia with +113.43%, and Bulgaria with +91.40%. The worst performers are Qatar with -41.91%, Uruguay with -54.55%, Indonesia with -79.24%, Uganda with -92.54%, and Botswana with -92.74%.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+145>

Performers	Countries	2016	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Ethiopia	0,5	2,3	1,8	360
	Colombia	0,9	2,8	1,9	211,1111
	North Macedonia	13,9	33,8	19,9	143,1655
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	6,7	14,3	7,6	113,4328
	Bulgaria	31,4	60,1	28,7	91,40127
Worse Performers	Qatar	33,4	19,4	-14	-41,9162
	Uruguay	1,1	0,5	-0,6	-54,5455
	Indonesia	42,4	8,8	-33,6	-79,2453
	Uganda	60,4	4,5	-55,9	-92,5497
	Botswana	12,4	0,9	-11,5	-92,7419

References

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR) e-ISSN*.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Angelo, L., & Matarrese, M. M. (2023). The intellectual assets in Europe. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 27(2), 1-13.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach. *Applied econometrics and international development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at SSRN 4355016.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. Available at SSRN 4021150.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. Available at SSRN 4420946.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post*.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. Available at SSRN 4061708.

